

INFINITE

BUILDINGRENOVATION

Industrialised envelope solutions

D5.3

Interactive market potential map

Public Report

Date – 30/04/2025

INFINITE/Industrialised durable building envelope retrofitting by all-in-one interconnected technology solutions project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No **958397**

D5.3 / Deliverable title

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Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the project partners who participated in the workshops, used the tool during its development and provided insightful feedback.

Document details

Deliverable No: D5.3

Dissemination level: Public

Work Package: WP5

Lead beneficiary: IVE

Date of publication: 30/04/2025

Version: 3.0

Version	Date	Comments	Authors
1.0	30/04/2023	Draft at M30	IVE & ONETEAM
1.1	26/02/2025	Drafting final version	IVE
1.2	12/03/2025	Review	ONETEAM
2.0	31/03/2025	Final version ready for review	IVE
2.1	08/04/2025	Review	EURAC
2.2	25/04/2025	Revision made based on the feedback received	IVE
3.0	29/04/2025	Final version approved by EURAC	IVE

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Project information

Title: Industrialised durable building envelope retrofitting by all-in-one interconnected technology solutions (INFINITE)

EC Grant Agreement Number: No 958397

Duration: November 2020 until April 2026 (66 months)

Coordinator

eurac
research

Project Partners

GreenDELTA

RUBNER

About the project

Off-site prefabrication of multifunctional envelopes has been shown to be a technically viable approach to increase rate and quality of deep renovation of residential buildings. However, several barriers are still preventing a massive adoption of prefabricated solutions.

INFINITE aims at boosting the building renovation sector through the so-called "**Renovation4.0**" approach, which leverages on both digitalisation and industrialisation to offer **tailor-made solutions** with a high level of **design freedom, decrease retrofit costs and time** thanks to the optimisation of the value-chain and **foster the adoption of eco-compatible long-lasting products** and systems.

To do so, the INFINITE Project relies on three main pillars:

1. cross-fertilisation from digitalisation trends in other markets (i.e. Industry4.0),
2. exploitation of industrial capabilities and coupling with LC-thinking approach
3. experience gained from the 1st generation of multifunctional prefabricated envelopes

INFINITE promotes a life cycle approach that allows for comprehensive design, optimisation of the O&M and depletion of end-of-life residual value.

INFINITE partners cover the whole renovation value-chain. Together, they will develop a new generation of residential building renovation products and actions centred on the all-in-one industrialised Life-Cycle-based approach. Expected outputs include:

- a set of multi-user and **multidisciplinary design tools**,
- **process-optimised all-in-one industrialised eco envelope kits**,
- **adaptive control systems**,
- set of **demand- and industry-side matched business models** to show the Renovation4.0 market potential,
- a **structured framework of entities and knowledge** able to clearly and widely demonstrate the Renovation4.0 benefits.

INFINITE will unleash the potential of the renovation industry by increasing the market penetration of sustainable, high-quality and long-lasting building retrofitting products and methods. This will ultimately contribute to the decarbonisation of the European building stock.

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Executive Summary

The **Interactive Market Potential Map**, developed within the INFINITE project, is a tool designed to support the **identification and assessment of renovation opportunities** across Europe. By integrating **digitalisation and industrialised renovation approaches**, the tool facilitates data-driven decision-making for home and building owners, building managers, architects, technicians, and industry professionals.

This document is intended to serve as a guide for using the tool. For additional guidance, a video tutorial can be found at:

https://youtu.be/7jMWn7AwG2A?si=oHQJGLU4Ziin_pNM

The first chapter introduces the tool.

The second chapter shows how to access the tool.

The following two chapters explain the two main functionalities offered by the platform:

- **Country-Level Analysis** – It enables users to compare key building characteristics across different countries through an **interactive colour-coded map**. By selecting parameters such as year of construction, heating system type, and ownership structure, users can quickly assess market trends and identify renovation potential on a national scale. The tool also allows users to **upload their own custom data sets**, ensuring a tailored and comprehensive analysis.
- **Building-Level Analysis** – It allows users to assess individual buildings for their **suitability for INFINITE's industrialised renovation solutions**. Users can locate a building on the map, enter relevant data, complete a questionnaire, and receive recommendations on applicable **renovation kits**. The tool also helps to identify **high potential areas** by mapping clusters of buildings that meet the criteria for industrialised renovation.

Through **intuitive data visualisation, structured analysis, and flexible customisation**, the **Interactive Market Potential Map** streamlines the process of identifying and assessing renovation opportunities. By increasing awareness and access to sustainable, high-quality renovation solutions, the tool contributes to **boosting energy efficiency and reducing carbon emissions** in the European building sector.

The final chapter provides an overview of the tool's capabilities in promoting **innovative, data-driven renovation strategies**, and introduces further exploitation and integration of services from other tools.

Users are encouraged to explore the platform to **gain market insights and uncover renovation opportunities**.

1. Introduction

The Interactive Market Potential Map is a tool designed to support dwelling/building owners, building managers, architects, technicians, and decision-makers in identifying renovation opportunities across Europe. By leveraging digitalisation and industrialised solutions, this tool enables users to assess renovation feasibility at both country and building levels. The tool aims also to facilitate the stakeholders in the evaluation of the replicability potential, applying the industrialised concept on a map based on EU building stock main features.

2. Accessing the Tool

The **Interactive Market Potential Map** is available at:

<https://infinite.oneteam.it/map/>

Upon accessing the URL, a **pop-up window** appears explaining the two main functionalities:

Figure 1 Market Potential Map home page

The two main functionalities included in the tool are:

- Country level analysis
- Building level analysis

Once the pop-up is closed, the country-level section is displayed by default.

3. Country-Level Analysis

This section of the tool allows users to compare building-related data across different countries. By selecting specific parameters, users generate a colour-coded map displaying relevant information for quick and intuitive comparisons.

3.1 Selecting parameters

Figure 2 Country level tab

To start an analysis, users must select the desired parameters from the top left-hand menu. The first selection (“Select subject”) determines the subsequent available options.

Figure 3 Selection of parameters

3.2 Available Data Categories

Users can analyse the following building characteristics:

- Physical Characteristics (e.g., year of construction, type of heating system)
- Building Typology (e.g., single-family or multi-family dwellings)
- HVAC System Types (e.g., electricity, gas, renewable sources)
- Existing Renewable Energy Systems
- Building Use and Ownership (e.g., residential, non-residential, owner-occupied, rented)

3.3 Data Visualisation

Once the parameters have been selected, a colour-coded map appears, showing data by country. The map allows users to:

- Adjust colour intensity for better visualisation
- Add or remove multiple data layers

As an example, the parameter "Physical building characteristics specific to each building" has been selected. Then, the "Year of construction", and the "Number of dwellings built between 1945 and 1969", so that the following map is displayed:

Figure 4 Number of dwellings built between 1945 and 1969 (thousands) map

Therefore, in this case, it can be assumed that there is a higher potential to renovate dwellings built during this period in Germany.

3.4 Uploading Custom Datasets

Users can integrate their own datasets by selecting the “Admin Dataset” button:

Figure 5 Admin Dataset button

Then, the next steps must be followed:

Figure 6 Interface for Admin Dataset

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1 - Download the provided **template** and fill it in.

Figure 7 Dataset template

For instance, the Eurostat's "Owner-occupied housing price index (2015=100)" has been included.

2 - Select the appropriate **building category** for mapping.

For example, to upload Eurostat's "Owner-occupied housing price index (2015=100)", the "Characteristics of the building related to its use and ownership" parameter is selected first, and then, the "Owned or rented homes" sub-parameter.

The following fields are then displayed:

A screenshot of the 'INFINITE Interactive market potential' Admin Dataset interface. The interface is dark-themed with light-colored text and buttons. At the top, there are three buttons: 'Download Template', 'Update', and 'Map', followed by a 'Create new Dataset' button. Below these are two dropdown menus for 'Parameters', with the first set to 'Characteristics of the building related to its use and ownership' and the second to 'Owned or rented homes'. A yellow bracket on the left side of the form groups the following fields: 'Insert description', 'Insert measure unit', 'Insert year', 'Insert source', and 'Insert source url'. A yellow circle with the number '3' is placed to the left of this bracket. At the bottom, there is a 'Check file' button, a 'Seleccionar archivo' button with the text 'Ningún archivo seleccionado', and a 'Clear Selection Menu' button. The interface also shows a table with columns for 'Country', 'Value', 'Year', and 'Error Message'.

Figure 8 Admin Dataset interface details

3 - Enter the **data details** (e.g., data description, unit of measure, year, source URL).

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4 - Upload the file with the dataset.

Figure 9 Admin Dataset interface example

5 - Check the data contained in the file to **validate the dataset**.

6 - Finally, import the data.

Figure 10 Import Data button

If something is found to be incorrect, the "Clear Selection Menu" can be used to restart the process.

Once the review is complete, the "Import Data" button must be pressed. When the process finishes, a pop-up window will display the message: "Dataset created". The dataset will then appear as a new selectable parameter within the tool.

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7 -To view the dataset, simply return to the **map**:

Figure 11 Return to Map button

8 - Then, select the appropriate parameter that was previously defined:

Figure 12 Selection of parameters

The map with the data will then be displayed:

Figure 13 Owner-occupied housing price index (2015=100) map

Finally, the data for each country can be easily compared at a glance. The colours are graded, with the darkest shade representing the highest value and the lightest indicating the lowest. In this example, Hungary has the highest index, while Italy has the lowest.

It should be noted that different layers can be created.

Following this example, the datasets of interest can be included in order to explore the market opportunities by country.

4. Building-Level Analysis

The aim of this section is to facilitate data-driven decisions on building renovations and to identify key opportunities for industrialised renovation approaches. Therefore, this tab allows users to:

- **Assess Building Feasibility** – Determine whether a particular building is suitable for industrialised renovation by following the assessment process provided.
- **Analyse High-Potential Areas** – Identify regions with a high concentration of buildings that could be renovated using industrialised solutions, i.e. areas with a high renovation potential.

Figure 14 Building level tab

4.1 Assessing Building Feasibility

To assess whether a building is suitable for INFINITE’s industrialised renovation solutions, these steps must be followed :

- 1- **Locate the building** by zooming in on the map (A) or entering its address in the search bar (B).

Figure 15 Add POI function

- 2 - Click **“Add POI”** and select the building to be evaluated by clicking on it on the map.

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3 - Fill in the **required building information** in the pop-up.

Once the building has been selected, its address is directly filled in.

Figure 16 Point Of Interest information window

4 - Press “**Save Point**” to confirm the selection.

5 - Fill in the **questionnaire** on the characteristics of the building (on the left of the screen):

Figure 17 Questionnaire on the characteristics of the building

6 - Click on “**INFINITE KITS**” to view the renovation solutions applicable to the building. Then, a window will be opened with the information of the KITS that can be installed:

Figure 18 INFINITE kits window

For additional details, the “**Read More**” button under each kit can be selected. This action will redirect the user to the [Industrialised Deep Retrofit HUB](#), where all the information about the kits can be found.

4.2 Identifying High-Potential Areas

By applying the above process to multiple buildings, the tool generates a **visual representation of the renovation potential** in a region. Users can apply filters to display only those buildings where specific renovation kits are feasible.

Figure 19 Filters to show the buildings in which determined KITs are feasible to be installed

5. Conclusion

The **Interactive Market Potential Map** tool has been developed within the framework of the H2020 INFINITE project. It is a **decision-making tool** that allows users to assess renovation opportunities at both the **country and building levels**. By leveraging digitalisation and industrialised solutions, this tool provides a **data-driven approach** to identify renovation opportunities and potential markets across Europe.

At the **country level**, the tool allows users to **compare key building characteristics** —such as year of construction, heating systems, and ownership status — using a **colour-coded interactive map**. Users can also **upload their own datasets**, allowing further customisation and deeper analysis of market trends.

At the **building level**, users can **assess individual buildings** by locating them on the map and completing a structured questionnaire. Based on the responses, the tool assesses the feasibility of implementing **INFINITE's innovative renovation technologies**, including smart glazing, prefabricated envelope kits, and integrated renewable energy systems. In addition, the tool helps to **identify high-potential areas** by visualising clusters of buildings that could benefit from industrialised renovation approaches.

By providing **intuitive data visualisation, tailored insights, and flexible analysis**, this tool supports **homeowners, building owners, building managers, architects, engineers and decision-makers** in optimising renovation strategies. Ultimately, it contributes to **accelerating the adoption of sustainable, high-quality retrofitting solutions** and support the **decarbonisation of the European building stock**.

Finally, the map has the potential to incorporate additional functionalities. One such link connects to the [Industrialised Deep Retrofit HUB](#), a platform that allows users to explore prefabricated, integrated façade solutions and see how these innovative systems are being applied in real buildings. The added value of this link is that users can quickly access information on the industrialised solutions featured on the map.

Another possibility to explore is to determine the **energy status of the selected building** and assess the **potential impact of renovating it with the industrialised kits**. This extension would further strengthen the tool's ability to support informed renovation decisions and optimise energy efficiency strategies.

More specifically, the tool is currently being linked to the [RENUEVA tool](#), which calculates the approximate energy consumption of a building and offers various improvement options for energy savings. The added value of linking the map to this tool is that it will provide the energy consumption of a building included in the map. This further development will be described in an annex to a future public INFINITE report entitled "Evaluation of INFINITE results implementation".